

Unlocking the Remediation Potential of Waste-Derived Biochar: Arsenic Shuttle between Groundwater and Environmentally Friendly Medium

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Problem with arsenic contamination (recognised by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC)) of aqueous systems is ubiquitous and alarming due to the various negative effects on human health [1]. Although the problem is widespread, the developing countries and rural areas are the most affected. In order to provide alternative (more affordable) solution, and promote circular economy and cleaner production, novel biochar was developed from abundant waste material from the oil industry – sunflower seed husks (SSH). SSH were iron (Fe)-functionalised and pyrolysed in order to convert into a magnetic biochar (FeBCH).

FeBCH was investigated for the removal of arsenate ((As (V)) from aqueous solutions and groundwater. Influence of solution pH (2-10), initial As (V) concentration (0.1-100 mg/L), contact time (5 min – 24 h) and FeBCH dosage (1-8 g/L) was examined in single model solutions. Effect of competing ions on As (V) removal was investigated in a model solution containing both, As (V) and phosphates which are assumed to be competitive for the active sites on the biochar surface. Finally, groundwater enriched with As (V) underwent adsorption tests indicating the future potential of obtained adsorbent for this purpose.

Results showed that As (V) adsorption was facilitated at pH values between 4 and 8. pH 6 was chosen for further experiments. A contact time of 4 h was sufficient for the removal of $91.6 \pm 1.2\%$ of As (V), while a small increase in removal efficiency (up to 5%) was observed after increasing contact time up to 24 h. The optimal biochar dosage was 2 g/L. Almost complete removal of arsenate was achieved for all initial concentrations. However, 20 mg/L was chosen as the initial concentration for further experiments. While As (V) reduction was hindered in the presence of competing phosphate ions (reached $47.2 \pm 0.5\%$ under previously determined optimal conditions and after 23 h of contact time), $83.8 \pm 1\%$ of As (V) was successfully removed from groundwater, indicating the good potential of synthesised biochar for the application in real systems.

References

- [1] X. Hu, Z. Ding, A. R. Zimmerman, S. Wang, and B. Gao, “Batch and column sorption of arsenic onto iron-impregnated biochar synthesized through hydrolysis,” *Water Res.*, vol. 68, pp. 206–216, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2014.10.009.

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